

Data Steward Career - Survey by ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) Community

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This report summarizes the findings from the Data Steward Career Survey, carried out as a part of ELIXIR Research Data Management Community. The survey was created with Google Forms 9. April to 13. May 2024 and advertised through the ELIXIR Research Data Management Community Slack space, mailing lists and through connected ELIXIR nodes. The aim of the survey is to understand the job profile of data stewards at ELIXIR and to understand what needs to be improved in the landscape in terms of career development and recognition. The survey is composed of following 15 questions. In total the survey has been answered 36 times. Results presented here are in aggregated form in order to reduce the risk of re-identification of participants through the questions.

Questions in the Survey

1. Which country are you based in?

Possible answers (drop down, mandatory):

- country names

2. Which type of institution are you working for?

Possible answers (Checkboxes, mandatory):

- University
- University Hospital
- Hospital
- Computing centre
- Research Institute
- State agency
- Private company
- Others (additional free text)

3. Which employment category are Data Stewards in your organisation employed as?

Possible answers (Checkboxes, mandatory):

- Scientific personnel
- Research support
- Technical personnel
- Administrative personnel
- Other (additional free text)

4. Does your job title say

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Data Steward
- Data Manager
- Data Engineer
- Engineer
- Researcher (e.g. Postdoc)
- Bioinformatician
- Data Coordinator
- Project Manager
- Team lead data management
- Data scientist
- Data analyst
- Other (additional free text)

5. Does your job title describe your role?

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Yes
- No

6. Is performance measurement for your job category reflecting your tasks and achievements? (e.g. for receiving pay raises or bonuses)

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

7. Would you like to comment on the performance measurement in your organisation for your job category?

(Text field, optional)

8. Is there a possibility in your organisation for vertical mobility as a data steward (junior, mid, senior roles)?

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Yes
- No

9. Is there a possibility in your organisation for horizontal mobility as a data steward (maintaining responsibilities, but increasing competencies and skills)?

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

10. What opportunities does your organization offer or should potentially offer for mobility within these/your role/positions?

Explanation: If you answered yes to either of the previous two questions on mobility, feel free to share your views here. Think about what potential pathways, criteria, and support mechanisms you think could be useful for career progression in capacity of your role.

(Text field, optional)

11. Which type of contract do you have?

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Permanent
- Fixed-term
- Permanent but depending on external funding
- Other (additional free text)

12. Do you have a formal certification (or formal education) for this type of work?

Possible answers (Multiple choice, mandatory):

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

13. Please specify formal certification/education or what other skills/qualifications you have that are added value for this type of work

(Text field, optional)

14. Your past job role(s)/title(s)

Possible answers (Checkboxes, mandatory):

- Wet-lab researcher
- Computational researcher
- Engineer
- Informatician/technical
- Software developer
- Data analysis
- Statistician
- Data Architect
- Data scientist
- Consultant
- Administrative officer
- Scientific officer
- Other (additional free text)

15. Your highest level of education in your original field

- PhD or equivalent
- MSc or equivalent
- BSc or equivalent
- Other (additional free text)

1 Geographical representation of replies received

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of replies

Table 1: Number of participants per country

Austria	1
Belgium	1
Estonia	1
Finland	3
France	1
Germany	1
Luxembourg	3
Netherlands	1
Norway	8
Portugal	2
Slovenia	1
Spain	5
Sweden	4
United Kingdom	4

Figure 1 presents the geographical distribution of survey responses, highlighting the regional representation of participants from ELIXIR nodes. The majority of responses are from Norway followed by Spain and the United Kingdom. The distribution reflects a lack of diverse spread which is due to the fact that data steward

role in life sciences is not yet common in across all the regions in Europe. However, as the snapshot of the geographical landscape, it shows which regions potentially require more outreach and support.

2 Type of hosting institutions

Figure 2 illustrates the types of hosting institutions for data stewards at ELIXIR (with combinations listed separately). While the figure shows a wide range of affiliations, universities and research institutes are the most common - this reflects the academic and research-oriented nature of the data stewardship roles. The presence of private companies and state agencies also indicates the cross-sector relevance of data stewardship. Diversity in hosting institutions underscores the interdisciplinary nature of data stewardship field; requiring a blend of research and administrative tasks, practical applications, and collaborative effort across different sectors.

3 Employment categories for Data Stewards

We asked the participants to state their employment category (Figure 3) in order to understand where do their host institutions place the role of data steward particularly since the data steward role is interdisciplinary and, in some regions/nodes, not well established and recognised. Out of all the categories and their combinations, scientific personnel dominate the responses, which aligns with the research-intensive nature of data stewardship. The combined categories reveal the hybrid roles that data stewards often have; blending technical, administrative, and scientific responsibilities. The responses also highlight the complex nature of data stewardship positions, emphasizing the need for versatile skills and the ability to operate across different domains.

4 Job titles for Data Steward Positions

Given the hybrid landscape of data steward role, the job titles for the role can vary from Data Manager and Data Coordinator to more specialized roles like Bioinformatician and FAIR lead (as shown in Figure 4). Again, this reflects that data stewardship encompasses roles that deal with not only data management and coordination but also technical support, policy-making, and scientific research. The diversity in job titles indicates the evolving nature of data stewardship, where roles are continuously being defined and refined based on organizational needs and advancements in the field.

5 Job title; does your job title describe your (data steward) role?

Does your job title describe your role?

Number of responses

Participants were asked whether their job titles accurately describe their data steward roles (Figure 5). Half of the participants indicated that their job title does reflect their role while remaining felt otherwise. This discrepancy suggests that while job titles may generally capture the essence of the roles, there are nuances and specific responsibilities that are not always conveyed. It is crucial to address this misalignment in order to improve job satisfaction and clarity in job functions and, equally importantly, to help organizations/institutions better recognize and support the contributions of their data stewards.

6 Is performance measurement for your job category reflecting your tasks and achievements? (e.g. for receiving pay raises or bonuses)

Performance measurement fit for role

Number of responses

The survey also inquired about the alignment of performance measurement with the tasks and achievements of data stewards (Figure 6). Majority of participants disagree that performance measurement for their job category reflects their tasks and achievements. This underscores the need to develop performance metrics and framework that are tailored to the responsibilities and contributions of data stewards. It also reflects the need for a supportive and conducive working environment that allows for recognising and rewarding the efforts of data stewards.

7 Would you like to comment on the performance measurement in your organisation for your job category?

```
## Warning: Using one column matrices in `filter()` was deprecated in dplyr 1.1.0.
## i Please use one dimensional logical vectors instead.
## This warning is displayed once every 8 hours.
## Call `lifecycle::last_lifecycle_warnings()` to see where this warning was
## generated.
```

Table 2: Answers to: “7. Would you like to comment on the performance measurement in your organisation for your job category?”

Define and assess own goals as part of annual development review. Not data specific.
 My achievements fall in-between the technical/administrative track and the scientific track. There is no fitting metric.
 There’s a year Performance and Development review but not sure there is a reward of any kind based on this. unavailable

It is non existing

Leader/supervisor based

Reports to the faculty head of the assigned faculties every six months about ongoing and finished projects, yearly reports on the whole data steward project to the rectorate

I am hired on a temporary basis hence vertical mobility etc doesn't really apply for me.

My tasks fall in between the two tracks (scientific & technical/administrative) and hence I do not check all boxes on either metric

not yet clear to me

performance measurement is mostly based on scientific publications, teaching and supervision of students, and public outreach activities

Self-reported, based on project engagements and general contributions to department's activities.

It is not very mature yet, as the roles have not yet been introduced to the organisations we are supporting.

I find this a complicated, quite generic question, so a bit difficult to answer. In our organisation performance is measured based on yearly planning and evaluation interviews, with the joint roadmap as content basis. In the case of myself and my team, this explicitly includes data (incl. FAIR) stewardship responsibilities, tasks and activities (they mainly sit in my team), which are evaluated and hence form the basis for pay raises (we don't have bonuses). We have recently formally started hiring staff as data stewards, I was informally the first data steward in our organisation (with a focus on community management; for my team is switching towards a metadata/semantic focus).

Informal but growing with the organisation

Wordcloud of answers to: "7. Would you like to comment on the performance measurement in your organisation for your job category?"

A word cloud of responses to the survey question. The words are arranged in a roughly circular pattern. The most prominent words, shown in the largest font, are 'based', 'data', 'performance', 'activities', 'development', 'reports', 'technicaladministrative', 'team', 'yet', 'yearly', 'track', 'focus', 'basis', 'hence', 'fall', 'organisation', 'scientific', 'review', 'steward', 'metric', 'project', and 'tasks'.

Figure 2: Would you like to comment on the performance measurement in your organisation for your job category?

8 Possibility for vertical mobility

Possibility for vertical mobility

Figure 8 examines the possibility for vertical mobility for data stewards; vertical career mobility refers to upward shift in a role based on level of responsibilities, for example, being promoted from junior to senior engineer. The responses indicate that the majority of the participants see limited opportunities for vertical mobility. This suggests that data stewards may view that their career progression is constrained within their current roles. This is due to a lack of clear career progression frameworks that organisations must work on, in addition to creating new opportunities for the next generation of data stewards.

9 Possibility for horizontal mobility

Possibility for horizontal mobility

Number of responses

The survey reveals a significant contrast in the perception of horizontal mobility among data stewards. While a considerable portion of respondents indicated that there is potential for horizontal mobility within their organizations, this perception is not uniformly held. A noticeable number of respondents expressed uncertainty or outright negation regarding the possibility of moving laterally to different roles. It is evident that both career mobility mobility types are areas of concern with differing nuances. Vertical mobility shows a somewhat more optimistic outlook among respondents. However, the split in responses suggests that both vertical and horizontal mobility possibilities are not easily accessible or recognized within organizations. Addressing these issues could significantly enhance career satisfaction and talent retention among data stewards.

10 Opportunities for mobility

Table 3: Answers to: “10. What opportunities does your organization offer or should potentially offer for mobility within these/your role/positions?”

No promotion, only re-grading. If a role appears to be required, can suggest we move into/create it
additional training: train-the-trainer, skills, conference attendance, etc - is all offered
Train-the-trainer, any other teaching competency leveling.
go abroad/mobility
Professional training is included in the position
Again, since I am a non-permanent staff member, such considerations do not apply.
Roles in different areas of the university.
data steward positions are not yet established
Time dedicated to professional development, flexibility in choosing engagements in external projects and internal activities based on professional interests.
Right now the mobility is not established. A promotion happens when a senior colleague is leaving.
Some clarifications: There’s no defined career or educational pathway for data stewards in Finland. However, there are plenty of specialists working in different roles in data stewardship in different research organisations. In my organisation mobility is supported but job title is rarely data steward. In addition, first ever national data stewardship training (course based) will begin in 2025 as a pilot, so this theme is very topical in Finland at the moment.
There are often wide range of internal calls open for new roles before they are opened as public calls. Sometimes it has been possible to take a leave of absence and work in some customer organisation to deepen expertise and also to help them utilize our services better.
We are offering training courses and participating to courses about topics we feel necessary for our job.
Involvement in different collaborative projects increases the horizontal mobility
I was able to move up based on taking leadership, my ability to think across teams/themes, and my ability to draft policies for the organisation, but also based on soft skills such as networking, communication skills, and people skills. And based on loyalty and hard work. Typical of our organisation is that most positions are combination positions (across teams/themes, such as FAIR, architecture, ELSI, services, company engagement, public policy & affairs), which allow for easy vertical and horizontal mobility: if you proof yourself, show interest, work hard, proof abilities, there are lots of opportunities to take and directions to grow into. This is actively supported by HR and theme leaders, and promoted from the start of your career.
Training and Maturity models

11 Which type of contract do you have

Type of contract

Number of responses

The type of contracts held by data stewards is varied, with a substantial number being on fixed-term contracts. There is also a significant portion on permanent contracts, although many of these are contingent on external funding. This instability in job security effects job satisfaction and long-term career planning, and organisations must address it. Relying on external funding could be the reason being career progression (vertical and horizontal mobility) not easily accessible and implemented. However, if want to ensure a motivated workforce and talent retention, organizations will need to consider more stable employment for current and next generation of data stewards.

12 Do you have a formal certification (or formal education) for this type of work?

Formal certification or education

Number of responses

■ Maybe ■ No ■ Yes

In terms of formal certification and education among data stewards, there is a varied landscape. While some have formal qualifications directly related to their roles, others rely on certifications that, while relevant, are not specifically tailored to data stewardship. This diversity suggests a need for a standardized and widely recognized certification programs to ensure that data stewards have the necessary skills and credentials. It is equally important to financially support data stewards in their current role, to gain certification for both interpersonal and management skills as this will help ensure smooth career progression.

13 Please specify formal certification/education or what other skills/qualifications you have that are added value for this type of work

Table 4: Answers to: “13 Please specify formal certification/education or what other skills/qualifications you have that are added value for this type of work?”

PhD in scientific discipline. Not in data management.
Dr. rer. nat. in Biology is highly relevant
DPO certification
MSc - know wet lab and sensitive data analysis problems firsthand. Train-the-Trainer
Data Steward course by BioData.pt
NordForsk/NeIC - FAIR Data Stewardship Course
Certificate Course Data Steward from the University of Vienna
30y + as a research engineer, handling data of all types.
NordForsk/NeIC - FAIR Data Stewardship Course

Data Protection officer certification Project Management | |Consulting experience and academic background | |Bs. Computer Science. PhD Biomedical Engineering | |FAIR Data Stewardship (Phortos Consultants) Forskningsdatahantering: tillgänglighet, hantering och samverkan (Högskolan i Borås) | |Bachelor of Science Degree in Astronomy, experience working with astronomical data sets, and experience curating an astronomy data archive. | |ISO 27005 certification as risk manager | |My background is in research and open science | |In addition to a masters degree in science I also have a vocational training in ICT-system development. | |PhD in Astrophysics, Big Data specialisation | |Research skills, communication skills, networking skills, leadership skills, service-orientation, FAIR skills | |Data management plan course; European proposal writing skills | |postgraduate in data management and stewardship practices IT project management and implementation | We asked participants about their formal certification or additional skills and qualification that serves as an added value to their data steward role. From PhDs in various scientific disciplines to specific certifications such as Data Protection Officer and FAIR Data Stewardship, the range of skills indicates that data stewardship requires a multifaceted skill set. This diversity can be a strength, but it also points to the need for organizations to clearly define the essential qualifications and ongoing training required for these roles.

14 Your past job role(s)/title(s)

Wordcloud of answers to: "14 Your past job role(s)/title(s)"

The word cloud depicting past job roles of respondents shows a wide range of previous positions, including researchers, engineers, consultants, and developers. The responses suggest that data stewardship attracts professionals from different academic backgrounds, this means the field is inclusive and has a space to foster innovative approaches to data management. However, it also means that tailored onboarding and professional development is required to be able to integrate varied experiences effectively.

15 Your highest level of education in your original field

Your highest level of education in your original field

Number of responses

The majority of data stewards at ELIXIR hold advanced degrees, reflecting the high level of expertise required in this field. Organizations should consider leveraging this high level of education by providing opportunities for data stewards to engage in research and development, further advancing their skills and contributing to bioinformatics infrastructure development. In addition, creating opportunities for data stewards without a PhD is a crucial step towards helping with career progression and developing an inclusive and diverse data stewardship landscape.

We thank all the participants for contributing to the survey, and the ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) community members to help with initial stages of preparing the survey. Through this report, we aimed to highlight key areas where data stewards experience both opportunities and challenges. The role of data steward is becoming increasingly important. Mobility, job security, formal education, and the diverse skill sets of data stewards are critical factors that organizations need to address to enhance career development and job satisfaction within this vital role.